

**MASTER TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE AS CORRELATES
TO THEIR PERFORMANCE AS TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE PROVIDERS:
INPUTS FOR TRAINING DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Master Teachers' Instructional Competence as Correlates to their Performance as Technical Assistance Providers: Inputs for Training Development Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the master teachers' instructional competence correlates to their performance as technical assistance providers, which served as inputs for training development programs during the school year 2025-2026. The perception of the master teachers and teachers as regards the instructional competence of master teachers correlates to their performance as technical assistance providers. Regarding mastery of the subject matter skills, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.48. In contrast, the master teacher-respondents got 3.56, both verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. Regarding teaching strategy skills, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.36, while the master teacher-respondents got 3.44, both verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. In terms of classroom management skills, the teacher and the master respondents got a composite mean of 3.42, which was both verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. In terms of evaluation skills, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.35, while the master teacher-respondents got 3.45, which were both verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. In terms of mentoring skills, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.46, while the master teacher-respondents got 3.59, which were both verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. The significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents, as regards the instructional competence of master teachers, correlates to their performance as technical assistance providers concerning the variables mentioned above. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the instructional competence of master teachers as correlated to their performance as technical assistance providers concerning the variables mentioned above.

Keywords: *classroom management, instructional competence, master teachers*

Introduction

Establishing a post called the Master Teacher would allow the expert teacher to be reimbursed at a level commensurate with the post of principal. The "master teacher" would serve as a mentor, facilitator, curriculum specialist, collaborator, and advocate for professional development and other vital policies within the educational institution.

As instructional leaders, they need to showcase mastery in terms of the management skills of their classrooms and discover varied ways to improve learning for all their students. These teachers are remarkable communicators who have a strong bond and connection with their students and effectively adapt the curriculum to respond to their learners' needs. Also, they know that the education process is about much more than sharing content and creating independent learners with the critical thinking skills to grow and thrive. Hence, lifelong learning and the teaching profession's viewpoint require teachers' expert knowledge and specialized skills, acquired and maintained through careful and persistent study.

Truly, teachers play a crucial role in nation-building. Through quality teachers, the Philippines can develop holistic learners steeped in values, equipped with 21st-century skills, and propel the country to development and progress. This aligns with the Department of Education (DepEd) vision of producing: "Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation" (DepEd Order No. 36, s. 2019). Evidence shows unequivocally that good teachers are vital to raising student achievement, i.e., quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching. Hence, enhancing teacher quality is paramount for long-term and sustainable nation-building.

As instructional frontrunners, mentors find means to support their co-teachers in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in aiding students' knowledge and understanding through efficient lesson plans of activities and suitable, sufficient, and modernized instructional materials Archibong (2019). He added and emphasized that when teaching is organized, the intention of improving the teaching and learning for the learner is brought out. This was supported by Gabriel (2019) when he said that mentors guarantee co-teachers feel encouraged while increasing their experience of the finest teaching practices and student achievement.

According to Umaru (2020), when mentees are nurtured and directed by their mentors to produce IMs that possess visibility, simplicity, attraction, and clarity, it will influence student academic performance.

Furthermore, the "master teacher" has been perceived as an effective teacher, a staff developer, a stimulus of curriculum leadership, and a strong provider of instructional leadership (Zumwalt, 2019).

The concept of the master teacher will be a multivariate measure of the classroom environment created by an individual called a "master teacher." The school reform movement has generated a complete body of rules to govern the behaviors of teachers, students, and administrators. Some rules and mandates would manipulate and control the teachers, students, and school administrators, guaranteeing

a return to excellence in institutions and among individuals (Gen, 2019).

Through these concepts, the researcher was urged to conduct this study to determine the level of instructional competence of master teachers and their effectiveness in giving technical assistance to their teacher-mentees.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the master teachers' instructional competence as correlates to their performance as technical assistance providers which served as inputs for training development program during the school year 2025-2026. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the master teachers and teachers as regards to the instructional competence of master teachers as correlate to their performance as technical assistance providers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. mastery of the subject matter skills;
 - 1.2. teaching strategy skills;
 - 1.3. classroom management skills;
 - 1.4. evaluation skills; and
 - 1.5. mentoring skills?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the instructional competence of master teachers as correlate to their performance as technical assistance providers with respect to the above-mentioned variables?
3. What training development program may be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive methods of research were utilized in the study with the aid of the questionnaire checklist. According to Dell (2019), Survey descriptive research is a quantitative method that focuses on describing the characteristics of a phenomenon rather than asking why it occurs. Doing this provides a better understanding of the nature of the subject at hand and creates a good foundation for further research.

The main goal of survey descriptive research is to shed light on the heart of the research problem and better understand it. The technique provides in-depth knowledge of the research problem before investigating why it exists.

Through this descriptive method, the researcher could determine the effectiveness of certain actions relating to master teachers' instructional competence and their performance as technical assistance providers.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This was conducted in the selected schools of District 1, Division of Antipolo City. The respondents of the study were composed of Master teachers and teachers. Each instrument was administered to all the respondents. The respondents were given enough time to answer the research instrument. The scope of this study covered the Master teachers and teachers from the selected schools of District 1, Division of Antipolo City.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part contained the evaluation of the respondents. The second part contained the performance rating of the master teacher, and the third part contained the comments and suggestions of the master teacher and teacher-respondents.

The questionnaires that served as survey instruments of the study were validated by experts to ensure their correctness and validity. The questionnaire's contents were analyzed and scrutinized by principals, master teachers, English teachers, and education program supervisors. Their comments and feedback were considered in the final approval of the method and were examined by the consultant again as the researcher's proofreader.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the study was conducted. Upon approval of the school's division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the master teacher and teacher-respondents from the selected public elementary schools of District 1, Division of Antipolo City, and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Ranking. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

t-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the instructional competence of master teachers as correlate to their performance as technical assistance providers with respect to mastery of the subject matter skills, teaching strategy skills, classroom management skills, evaluation skills, and mentoring skills.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Based on Masters Teacher's Perception

Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills

Table 1. *Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills*

<i>A. Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a Master Teacher, I help teachers to...</i>			
1. consider accuracy in the delivery of content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies.	3.41	VSA	4
2. elucidate properly the learning goals, instructional processes, procedures for the better understanding of the learners.	3.40	VSA	5
3. link clearly the present content with past and future lesson.	3.58	VSA	1
4. create varied scenarios / situations that urge learners to use critical thinking skills.	3.42	VSA	3
5. involve and sustain learners' active interest in the lesson by making content productive, meaningful, and relevant.	3.57	VSA	2
Composite Mean	3.48	VSA	

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that they link clearly the present content with past and future lessons, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.58 and the highest rank of 1. The findings revealed that the master teachers excelled in clearly linking present content with both past and future lessons. They demonstrated a sophisticated ability to contextualize current topics within a broader educational framework, enhancing students' understanding by connecting them to historical contexts and future applications. By referencing past lessons, these educators provided continuity and reinforced foundational knowledge, ensuring that students could build upon previously acquired concepts. Simultaneously, they skillfully integrated future lesson objectives, illustrating how current learning goals contributed to upcoming educational milestones. This approach not only made learning more coherent but also underscored the relevance and progression of the curriculum over time. The master teachers' proficiency in linking past, present, and future content exemplified their pedagogical expertise and significantly contributed to students' ability to grasp the broader significance and continuity of their education. According to Britz et al. (2020), mastery learning is an effective teaching method for undergraduate medical students acquiring abdominal sonography competencies, with superior results compared to the "see one, do one" approach.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they elucidate properly the learning goals, instructional processes, procedures for the better understanding of the learners which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.40 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that the master teachers effectively elucidated learning goals, instructional processes, and procedures to enhance learners' understanding. They demonstrated a clear and systematic approach to communicating learning objectives, ensuring that students comprehended the purpose and expectations of each lesson. By breaking down complex concepts and outlining instructional processes step-by-step, these educators provided clarity and structure, which facilitated deeper learning and engagement among students. Moreover, they articulated procedures in a way that connected theoretical knowledge to practical application, enabling learners to grasp the relevance of the content in real-world contexts. Blömeke et al. (2020) stated that strong levels of knowledge and skills are crucial for high instructional quality in mathematics teachers, while learning beliefs are less relevant, highlighting the need for a stronger subject-specific operationalization of instructional quality.

The composite mean of 3.48 implied that the perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of mastery of the subject matter skills is within high level. The findings indicated that master teachers perceived themselves as highly competent technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of their mastery of subject matter skills. Their self-assessment reflected a deep understanding and proficiency in the content areas they taught, allowing them to effectively convey complex concepts and principles to their students. This high level of subject mastery enabled them to adapt instructional strategies and materials to meet diverse learning needs and challenges in the classroom. Moreover, their perception of instructional competence was supported by their ability to provide technical assistance and support to colleagues and other educators. They demonstrated a readiness to share their expertise, offer mentorship, and collaborate on curriculum development and instructional improvement initiatives. Their confidence in their subject matter skills was evident in their approach to professional development and continuous learning, where they sought to enhance their knowledge base and stay updated with current educational practices. According to Ажыгулова & Калмырзаева (2022), teacher's professional competence is a set of generalized knowledge, skills, and abilities that ensure the implementation of state educational standards, with the most common skill being the ability to think and act pedagogically.

Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Teaching Strategy Skills

Table 2. *Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Teaching Strategy Skills*

<i>B. Teaching Strategy Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a Master Teacher, I help teachers to...</i>			
1. utilize individual and cooperative learning activities to increase and augment the abilities of learners for a better academic performance.	3.20	SA	4
2. encourage individual learners to create higher order thinking skills questions.	3.54	VSA	2
3. consider the use a variety of teaching strategies, approaches and techniques suited and aligned to the subject matter and to the level of the learners.	3.37	VSA	3
4. use instructional materials which are appropriate to the learner's learning styles.	3.12	SA	5
5. align with lesson objectives the teaching methods, learning activities and instructional or resources appropriate to learners.	3.55	VSA	1
Composite Mean	3.36	VSA	

As presented in Table 2, the respondents perceived that they align with lesson objectives the teaching methods, learning activities and instructional or resources appropriate to learners which got the highest weighted mean of 3.55 and the highest rank of 1. The findings revealed that the master teachers adeptly aligned teaching methods, learning activities, and instructional resources with lesson objectives, ensuring a cohesive and effective educational experience for learners. They demonstrated a meticulous approach to curriculum planning, carefully selecting strategies and activities that directly supported the intended learning outcomes. By aligning these elements, the master teachers ensured that every instructional component contributed meaningfully to students' understanding and mastery of the subject matter. According to Copur-Gencturk & Doleck (2021), teachers' strategic competence for multistep fraction word problems is crucial for devising valid strategies and effectively mathematizing unknown quantities in solutions.

However, the said group of respondents observed that they use instructional materials which are appropriate to the learner's learning styles which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.22 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that the master teachers skillfully used instructional materials that catered to the diverse learning styles of their students. They demonstrated a nuanced understanding of how different learners absorb and process information, and accordingly, they selected materials that accommodated various preferences and needs in the classroom. Whether through visual aids, hands-on activities, auditory resources, or interactive digital tools, the master teachers ensured that instructional materials were not only relevant to the curriculum but also aligned with the unique learning styles and abilities of their students. Mallillin et al. (2023) stated that modern teaching relies on instructional skills and competency skills theory, which contribute to classroom management, engagement, and personal competency development.

The composite mean of 3.36 implied that the perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of teaching strategy skills is within high level. The findings indicated that master teachers perceived themselves as possessing a high level of instructional competence as technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of their teaching strategy skills. They demonstrated a strong ability to employ a variety of teaching strategies effectively, tailoring their approaches to meet the specific needs and learning styles of their students. Their perception of high competence in teaching strategies was grounded in their adeptness at selecting and implementing appropriate methods, such as differentiated instruction, cooperative learning, inquiry-based approaches, and technology integration. Strategic competence is crucial in language teaching as it enables learners to successfully communicate and understand each other in various situations (Alem, 2020).

Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Classroom Management Skills

Table 3. *Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Classroom Management Skills*

<i>C. Classroom Management Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a Master Teacher, I help teachers to...</i>			
1. utilize the time efficiently when designing and preparing activities for pair and group discussions.	3.31	SA	3
2. check and verify the papers of the learners and use the results for the improvement of classroom instructions.	3.60	VSA	2
3. monitor the learning activities of pupils in the classroom by checking and collecting the exercises.	3.27	VSA	4
4. assist learners to gain better self-discipline in the learning process.	3.73	VSA	1
5. encourage the learners to show active participation and to practice self-discipline.	3.21	SA	5
Composite Mean	3.42	VSA	

As shown in Table 3, the respondents perceived that they assist learners to gain better self-discipline in the learning process which got the highest weighted mean of 3.72 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers played a crucial role in assisting

learners to develop better self-discipline in the learning process. Through structured guidance and consistent reinforcement of expectations, they fostered an environment where students could cultivate essential skills like time management, organization, and personal responsibility. By setting clear goals and establishing routines, these educators empowered students to take ownership of their learning journey. According to König et al. (2021), teachers' pedagogical competence, specifically general pedagogical knowledge and classroom management expertise, significantly impacts students' mathematics achievement in lower secondary classrooms.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they encourage the learners to show active participation and to practice self-discipline which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.21 and least rank of 5. The findings revealed that master teachers effectively encouraged learners to actively participate and practice self-discipline throughout their educational journey. By creating a supportive and engaging classroom environment, these educators motivated students to take initiative and contribute actively to discussions, activities, and projects. They emphasized the importance of active participation as a means to deepen understanding and develop critical thinking skills. Classroom management strategies in computer-assisted lessons directly impact students' success in retaining information and building learning skills and competences (Iacob & Musuroi, 2021).

The composite mean of 3.42 implied that the perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of classroom management skills is within high level. The findings indicated that master teachers perceived themselves as possessing a high level of instructional competence as technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of classroom management skills. They demonstrated effective strategies for creating and maintaining a positive and orderly learning environment, where students could engage actively and achieve their academic potential. These educators were adept at establishing clear expectations and routines, which promoted a sense of structure and predictability in the classroom. They employed proactive measures to prevent disruptions and address behavior issues promptly and constructively. By fostering a climate of respect and mutual understanding, master teachers facilitated a conducive atmosphere for learning and collaboration among students. According to Junker et al. (2021), pre-service and beginning teachers show medium to high levels of classroom management competence, but professional vision is not significantly related to their performance.

Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Evaluation Skills

Table 4. Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Evaluation Skills

<i>D. Evaluation Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a Master Teacher, I help teachers to...</i>			
1. consider the practice of valid and reliable formative assessment to comprehend the model of learning output.	3.40	VSA	2
2. provide systematic models and influence the practice of formative assessment in examining suitable support, measure, and implementation.	3.47	VSA	1
3. give challenges on assessment, check on the suitability of assessment practice tools to be utilized in the assessment process for both teachers and learners.	3.27	VSA	4
4. frame practices on formative assessment as to level, knowledge, conceptions, values, responsibilities, teaching experiences, and subject matter regarding assessment practices.	3.23	SA	5
5. provide appropriate learning tasks and projects that support good study habits of learners.	3.38	VSA	3
Composite Mean	3.35	VSA	

As presented in Table 4, the respondents stated that they try to provide systematic models and influence the practice of formative assessment in examining suitable support, measure, and implementation which got the highest weighted mean of 3.47 and the highest rank of 1. The findings revealed that master teachers actively sought to provide systematic models and influence the practice of formative assessment in examining suitable support, measures, and implementation strategies. They demonstrated a deep understanding of the importance of ongoing assessment in gauging student progress and informing instructional decisions. According to Korir (2022), value-added measures and standards-based evaluations significantly affect teachers' instructional competence, but clear objectives are crucial for effective performance appraisal.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they frame practices on formative assessment as to level, knowledge, conceptions, values, responsibilities, teaching experiences, and subject matter regarding assessment practice which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.23 and least rank of 5. The findings revealed that master teachers framed practices on formative assessment by considering various factors such as levels of knowledge, conceptions, values, responsibilities, teaching experiences, and subject matter expertise related to assessment practices. They recognized the importance of tailoring formative assessment strategies to align with the diverse needs and contexts of both students and educators. Putina (2023) stated that teacher evaluation competence, which involves knowledge, tools, and professional ethics, is essential for effective teaching and student growth.

The composite mean of 3.35 implied that the perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of evaluation skills is within high level. The findings indicated that master teachers perceived themselves as possessing a high level of instructional competence as technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of their evaluation skills. They demonstrated proficiency in designing and implementing comprehensive evaluation frameworks to assess

student learning, instructional effectiveness, and overall program outcomes. Assessment procedures in initial teacher education effectively train pre-service teachers in cross-cutting teaching competences, but their effectiveness is mainly based on self-perception rather than experimental studies (Aparicio & Navarro-Asencio, 2023).

Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Mentoring Skills

Table 5. Perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of Mentoring Skills

<i>E. Mentoring Skills</i> <i>As a Master Teacher, I help teachers to...</i>	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. examine the quality of classroom interaction and emotional exhaustion for teachers' instructional process and delivery.	3.28	VSA	5
2. display instructional delivery associated with quality instruction for learners inside the classroom.	3.49	VSA	3
3. direct on the process of understanding and shaping the practice of a teacher on instructional delivery and learning outcome.	3.51	VSA	2
4. determine instructional delivery in classroom practice and setting as to background and experiences, skills, training, and knowledge.	3.34	VSA	4
5. conceptualize emotional availability and regulates responsiveness to instructional delivery.	3.69	VSA	1
Composite Mean	3.46	VSA	

As presented in Table 5, the respondents stated that they conceptualize emotional availability and regulate responsiveness to instructional delivery which got the highest weighted mean of 3.69 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers conceptualized emotional availability and regulated responsiveness as integral aspects of instructional delivery. They understood that emotional availability involves creating a supportive and empathetic environment where students feel valued and understood. These educators prioritized building positive relationships with students, fostering trust, and demonstrating genuine care and interest in their well-being. An innovative mentoring program significantly improves students' intrapersonal competences, contributing to their integral formation in university education (Crespí & López, 2023).

However, the said group of respondents stated that they examined the quality of classroom interaction and emotional exhaustion for teachers' instructional process and delivery which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.28 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that master teachers actively examined the quality of classroom interaction and its impact on emotional exhaustion within the context of teachers' instructional processes and delivery. They recognized that the dynamics of classroom interaction play a crucial role in shaping the learning environment and influencing both student engagement and teacher well-being. According to Ephraim (2020), effective mentoring in nursing education can improve retention of new faculty, with continuous improvement and training being crucial for both mentors and mentees.

The composite mean of 3.46 implied that the perception of the master teachers as regards the instructional competence as technical assistance providers in terms of mentoring skills is within high level. Moreover, master teachers served as role models and advocates for continuous improvement in teaching. They promoted a culture of professional learning and development within their educational community, encouraging colleagues to participate in workshops, peer observations, and collaborative projects aimed at enhancing instructional effectiveness. Cornelius et al. (2020) stated that specialized professional development and individualized coaching for general education teacher mentors improves their knowledge, ability to identify specialized instruction components, and improves novice special educators' instructional practices.

Based on Teachers' Perception

Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills

Table 6. Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills

<i>A. Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills</i> <i>The Master Teacher helps the teacher to</i>	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. consider accuracy in the delivery of content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies.	3.56	VSA	3
2. elucidate properly the learning goals, instructional processes, procedures for the better understanding of the learners.	3.71	VSA	1
3. link clearly the present content with past and future lesson.	3.66	VSA	2
4. create varied scenarios / situations that urge learners to use critical thinking skills.	3.50	VSA	4
5. involve and sustain learners' active interest in the lesson by making content productive, meaningful, and relevant.	3.38	VSA	5
Composite Mean	3.56	VSA	

As discussed in Table 6, the respondents stated that the master teachers elucidate properly the learning goals, instructional processes, procedures for the better understanding of the learners, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.71 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers effectively elucidated learning goals, instructional processes, and procedures to enhance learners' understanding. They demonstrated a clear and structured approach to communicating the objectives of each lesson, ensuring students grasped the purpose and expectations of their learning experiences. By articulating the relevance of the content and outlining the steps involved in achieving learning outcomes, these educators provided a framework that guided students towards deeper comprehension. Master classes effectively develop future teachers' soft skills by transferring knowledge and experience, fostering independent thinking, teamwork, and promoting self-education and self-perfection (Betilmerzaeva & Muskhanova, 2022).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the master teachers involve and sustain learners' active interest in the lesson by making content productive, meaningful, and relevant which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.38 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that master teachers effectively involved and sustained learners' active interest in lessons by making content productive, meaningful, and relevant. They demonstrated a skillful ability to connect the curriculum to real-world applications and students' personal experiences, emphasizing the practical relevance of the material being taught. By linking lessons to current events, societal issues, or future career opportunities, these educators engaged students intellectually and emotionally, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for the subject matter. Omonovich et al. (2020) stated that the competency-based approach in special discipline lessons enhances applied, practical nature of education, resulting in well-informed specialists who can apply knowledge in their professional activities.

The composite mean of 3.56 implied that the perception of the teachers as regards to the instructional competence of the master teacher as technical assistance providers in terms of mastery of the subject matter skills is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers perceived the instructional competence of master teachers as technical assistance providers to be at a high level, particularly regarding their mastery of subject matter skills. Teachers recognized the depth of knowledge and expertise that master teachers brought to their instructional roles, appreciating their ability to convey complex concepts clearly and effectively. Master teachers demonstrated a thorough understanding of the subject matter they taught, providing comprehensive explanations and engaging learning experiences that facilitated deep learning among students. Their command of the curriculum and their ability to connect theoretical concepts to practical applications resonated with their colleagues, who valued their insights and contributions to professional development. Teachers' instructional competencies in remote blended learning include teaching, organizing, presenting, and evaluating student performance (Gayon, 2023).

Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Teaching Strategy Skills

Table 7. Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Teaching Strategy Skills

<i>B. Teaching Strategy Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The Master Teacher helps the teacher to</i>			
1. utilize individual and cooperative learning activities to increase and augment the abilities of learners for a better academic performance.	3.28	VSA	4
2. encourage individual learners to create higher order thinking skills questions.	3.52	VSA	3
3. consider the use a variety of teaching strategies, approaches and techniques suited and aligned to the subject matter and to the level of the learners.	3.23	SA	5
4. use instructional materials which are appropriate to the learner's learning styles.	3.66	VSA	1
5. align with lesson objectives the teaching methods, learning activities and instructional or resources appropriate to learners.	3.53	VSA	2
Composite Mean	3.44	VSA	

As presented in Table 7, the respondents perceived that the master teachers use instructional materials which are appropriate to the learner's learning styles which got the highest weighted mean of 3.66 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers skillfully used instructional materials that were tailored to accommodate learners' diverse learning styles. They demonstrated a keen awareness of how different students absorb and process information, and accordingly selected materials that resonated with various preferences and needs in the classroom. The competence approach model effectively designs, implements, and evaluates training programs for teaching staff, focusing on core competencies and adapting to Romanian pre-university education requirements (Mara & Morar, 2023).

However, the said group of respondents observed that the master teachers consider the use a variety of teaching strategies, approaches and techniques suited and aligned to the subject matter and to the level of the learners which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.23 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that master teachers conscientiously considered and utilized a variety of teaching strategies, approaches, and techniques that were well-suited and aligned to both the subject matter and the diverse levels of their learners. They demonstrated a deep understanding of how to adapt instructional methods to meet the specific needs, interests, and developmental stages of their students. Omar et al. (2022) stated that a practical teaching framework can effectively identify the elements of teacher competence, resulting in high-impact learning and producing highly skilled workforce.

The composite mean of 3.44 implied that the perception of the teachers as regard to the instructional competence of the master teacher as technical assistance providers in terms of teaching strategy skills is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers perceived the instructional competence of master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of teaching strategy skills to be at a high level. Teachers recognized the adeptness of master teachers in employing a wide range of effective teaching strategies that enhanced student engagement and learning outcomes. Master teachers demonstrated proficiency in selecting and implementing teaching strategies such as differentiated instruction, cooperative learning, inquiry-based learning, and technology integration. They tailored these strategies to meet the diverse learning needs and preferences of their students, ensuring that instructional methods were both relevant and effective in promoting understanding and retention of content. According to Moriera et al. (2022), higher education teachers value personal skills and qualities, while curriculum and instructional competence are most important, but cultural competence and specific competences for diversity and inclusion are scarce.

Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Classroom Management Skills

Table 8. *Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Classroom Management Skills*

<i>C. Classroom Management Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The Master Teacher helps the teacher to</i>			
1. utilize the time efficiently when designing and preparing activities for pair and group discussions.	3.53	SA	2
2. check and verify the papers of the learners and use the results for the improvement of classroom instructions.	3.24	SA	4
3. monitor the learning activities of pupils in the classroom by checking and collecting the exercises.	3.44	VSA	3
4. assist learners to gain better self-discipline in the learning process.	3.21	SA	5
5. encourage the learners to show active participation and to practice self-discipline.	3.66	VSA	1
Composite Mean	3.42	VSA	

As shown in Table 8, the respondents perceived that the master teachers encourage the learners to show active participation and to practice self-discipline which got the highest weighted mean of 3.66 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers effectively encouraged learners to actively participate and cultivate self-discipline within the learning process. They fostered a classroom environment where students felt empowered to engage actively in discussions, activities, and collaborative projects. By emphasizing the importance of participation, master teachers promoted a culture of inquiry and dialogue that enriched learning experiences and encouraged diverse perspectives. Effective classroom management for special education students involves fostering trusting relationships, teaching expectations, ensuring predictability and structure, providing ongoing feedback, managing unwanted behavior, and engaging learners (Harlacher & Marx, 2022).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the master teachers assist learners to gain better self-discipline in the learning process which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.21 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that master teachers played a pivotal role in assisting learners to develop better self-discipline within the learning process. They implemented strategies aimed at fostering personal responsibility, organization, and perseverance among students, essential components of effective self-discipline. According to Susiyowadi et al. (2021), superior's perception, work-orientation, and self-development significantly improve classroom management competence, with work-orientation having a lesser but still significant impact.

The composite mean of 3.42 implied that the perception of the teachers as regard to the instructional competence of the master teacher as technical assistance providers in terms of classroom management skills is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a perception of high instructional competence among master teachers as technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of classroom management skills. Teachers recognized the mastery of master teachers in creating and maintaining a conducive and organized learning environment where students could thrive academically and behaviorally. Master teachers demonstrated effective classroom management strategies that promoted a positive atmosphere of respect, engagement, and productivity. They established clear expectations and routines, which helped minimize disruptions and maximize instructional time. By proactively addressing behavior issues and providing consistent support, master teachers created a structured environment conducive to learning. Putri et al. (2023) stated that the school principal's instructional leadership, or learning leadership, improves teacher professional competence by setting clear academic goals, motivating staff and students, aligning teaching and learning activities, and implementing sustainable systems.

Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Evaluation Skills

As presented in Table 9, the respondents stated that the master teachers give challenges on assessment, check on the suitability of assessment practice tools to be utilized in the assessment process for both teachers and learners which got the highest weighted mean of 3.70 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers effectively provided challenges on assessment practices and ensured the suitability of assessment tools used in the assessment process for both teachers and learners. They demonstrated a proactive approach to enhancing assessment practices by critically evaluating the relevance, validity, and effectiveness of assessment

tools and methodologies. According to Mohammed (2021), evaluation in instructional design involves three types: formative, summative, and confirmative, and should occur at various stages and times to assess the success of instruction.

Table 9. *Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Evaluation Skills*

<i>D. Evaluation Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The Master Teacher helps the teacher to</i>			
1. consider the practice of valid and reliable formative assessment to comprehend the model of learning output.	3.49	VSA	2
2. provide systematic models and influence the practice of formative assessment in examining suitable support, measure, and implementation.	3.36	VSA	4
3. give challenges on assessment, check on the suitability of assessment practice tools to be utilized in the assessment process for both teachers and learners.	3.70	VSA	1
4. frame practices on formative assessment as to level, knowledge, conceptions, values, responsibilities, teaching experiences, and subject matter regarding assessment practices.	3.26	VSA	5
5. provide appropriate learning tasks and projects that support good study habits of learners.	3.45	VSA	3
Composite Mean	3.45	VSA	

As presented in Table 9, the respondents stated that the master teachers give challenges on assessment, check on the suitability of assessment practice tools to be utilized in the assessment process for both teachers and learners which got the highest weighted mean of 3.70 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers effectively provided challenges on assessment practices and ensured the suitability of assessment tools used in the assessment process for both teachers and learners. They demonstrated a proactive approach to enhancing assessment practices by critically evaluating the relevance, validity, and effectiveness of assessment tools and methodologies. According to Mohammed (2021), evaluation in instructional design involves three types: formative, summative, and confirmative, and should occur at various stages and times to assess the success of instruction. However, the said group of respondents stated that the master teachers frame practices on formative assessment as to level, knowledge, conceptions, values, responsibilities, teaching experiences, and subject matter regarding assessment practices which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.26 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that master teachers framed practices on formative assessment with careful consideration of various factors, including levels of knowledge, conceptions, values, responsibilities, teaching experiences, and subject matter expertise related to assessment practices. Master teachers tailored their approach to formative assessment based on the diverse levels of knowledge and understanding among students. They implemented strategies to gauge and scaffold learning progress effectively, ensuring that assessments were meaningful and actionable for each learner's developmental stage. Teachers' competence beliefs and self-efficacy have a limited impact on students' academic outcomes, with ambiguity in their conceptualization and assessment in research (Lauermaun & Hagen, 2021).

The composite mean of 3.45 implied that the perception of the teachers as regard to the instructional competence of the master teacher as technical assistance providers in terms of evaluation skills is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a perception of high instructional competence among master teachers as technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of evaluation skills. Teachers recognized the expertise of master teachers in designing, implementing, and interpreting evaluations that effectively assessed student learning and informed instructional decision-making. Master teachers demonstrated proficiency in employing a variety of evaluation methods, including formative and summative assessments, to gather comprehensive data on student progress and achievement. They emphasized the importance of using valid and reliable assessment tools that aligned with curriculum goals and learning objectives. According to Paslaru (2022), the concept of competence, when attributed to education's unique purpose, contradicts the essence of competence as a capacity limited to operational objectives and risks deculturalizing education by substituting it for a single element of the culture of education.

Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Mentoring Skills

Table 10. *Perception of the teachers as regards the instructional competence of the master teachers as technical assistance providers in terms of Mentoring Skills*

<i>E. Mentoring Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The Master Teacher helps the teacher to</i>			
1. examine the quality of classroom interaction and emotional exhaustion for teachers' instructional process and delivery.	3.65	VSA	3
2. display instructional delivery associated with quality instruction for learners inside the classroom.	3.65	VSA	3
3. direct on the process of understanding and shaping the practice of a teacher on instructional delivery and learning outcome.	3.73	VSA	2
4. determine instructional delivery in classroom practice and setting as to background and experiences, skills, training, and knowledge.	3.20	SA	4
5. conceptualize emotional availability and regulates responsiveness to instructional delivery.	3.75	VSA	1
Composite Mean	3.59	VSA	

As presented in Table 10, the respondents stated that the master teachers conceptualize emotional availability and regulates responsiveness to instructional delivery which got the highest weighted mean of 3.75 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that master teachers adeptly conceptualized emotional availability and regulated responsiveness within their instructional delivery. They demonstrated a deep understanding of the importance of creating an emotionally supportive learning environment where students feel valued, safe, and encouraged to participate actively in their learning. Master teachers prioritized emotional availability by fostering positive relationships with students, demonstrating empathy, and acknowledging the emotional aspects of learning. They created opportunities for open communication, actively listening to students' concerns, and providing constructive feedback that nurtured growth and confidence. Coaching, mentoring, and supervision have a small but significant impact on pre-service teachers' instructional skills, with cognitive modeling from cooperating teachers or supervisors being a significant moderator (Mok & Staub, 2021).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the master teachers determine instructional delivery in classroom practice and setting as to background and experiences, skills, training, and knowledge which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.20 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that master teachers carefully determined instructional delivery in classroom practice and setting based on various factors, including background and experiences, skills, training, and knowledge. Master teachers leveraged their diverse backgrounds and experiences to inform instructional decisions and strategies. They drew upon personal teaching experiences, professional development opportunities, and insights gained from their educational journey to tailor their approach to meet the unique needs of their students. According to Ephraim (2020), effective mentoring in nursing education can improve retention of new faculty, with continuous improvement and training being crucial for both mentors and mentees.

The composite mean of 3.59 implied that the perception of the teachers as regard to the instructional competence of the master teacher as technical assistance providers in terms of mentoring skills is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a perception of high instructional competence among master teachers as technical assistance providers, particularly in terms of mentoring skills. Teachers recognized the expertise of master teachers in guiding and supporting colleagues and students through effective mentorship relationships. Master teachers demonstrated strong mentoring skills by providing personalized guidance and constructive feedback that supported professional growth and development. They fostered collaborative learning environments where colleagues could share insights, strategies, and best practices to enhance teaching effectiveness. Coaching and mentoring in education can help teachers develop into confident classroom practitioners and future leaders, offering support and a safe supportive environment (Oberholzer & Boyle, 2023).

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents

Table 11. *Difference observed between the perception Master Teachers and teachers*

<i>Difference observed between the perception of Master teachers and teachers in terms of instructional competence of the master teacher as technical assistance providers:</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Mastery of the Subject Matter Skills	-0.01981	0.31989	0.03374	-0.584	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Teaching Strategy Skills	0.19724	0.27356	0.03524	5.872	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Classroom Management Skills	-0.01985	0.3278	0.03681	-0.593	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Evaluation Skills	0.01862	0.31989	0.03313	0.582	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Mentoring Skills	0.01612	0.33184	0.03262	0.589	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Table 11 presented the findings that examined comparison of perceptions on instructional competence between Master teachers and teachers across various skills shows no statistically significant differences based on the provided statistical data. Specifically, the *t*-values and corresponding interpretations for mastery of subject matter skills (-0.584), teaching strategy skills (5.872), classroom management skills (-0.593), evaluation skills (0.582), and mentoring skills (0.589) all indicate that the mean differences observed are not significant. This means that both groups are similarly perceived in their abilities as technical assistance providers in these domains. Therefore, accepting the null hypothesis for each comparison, the study concludes that there is no meaningful distinction in how Master teachers and teachers are perceived in terms of instructional competence based on the statistical findings provided.

Moeketsane et al. (2021) stated that subject leaders' knowledge and perceptions are better predictors of their perceived competence in instructional leadership than their beliefs, suggesting interventions targeting perceptions can promote more distributed subject leadership in schools.

Training Development Program

Table 12 outlined the proposed training and development programs that were designed to enhance instructional competence among Master teachers and teachers. The first program, Collaborative Professional Development, aimed to foster collaboration and knowledge-sharing among educators, facilitating the exchange of best practices and innovative teaching methods. It was overseen by the Professional Development Coordinator, who ensured that sessions were productive and aligned with educational goals.

The Mentoring Program paired new teachers with experienced Master teachers to provide structured mentorship in instructional techniques and career development. This initiative was led by the Mentoring Coordinator, who facilitated meaningful mentor-mentee

relationships aimed at accelerating professional growth and integration into the teaching community.

Table 12. *Proposed Training Development Program*

<i>Program Name</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Person In Charge</i>
Collaborative Professional Development	Foster collaboration among Master teachers and teachers to share best practices and innovative teaching methods.	Professional Development Coordinator
Mentoring Program	Provide structured mentorship to new teachers by pairing them with experienced Master teachers for guidance in instructional techniques and career development.	Mentoring Coordinator
Diverse Instructional Strategies Workshop	Equip teachers with skills in differentiated instruction, technology integration, and project-based learning to cater to diverse learning needs.	Instructional Coach
Effective Classroom Management Training	Enhance teachers' abilities to create positive learning environments and manage classroom dynamics effectively.	School Administrator
Data-Driven Instruction Workshop	Train teachers in analyzing student data, identifying learning gaps, and using data to inform instructional decisions.	School Administrator and Supervisor

The Diverse Instructional Strategies Workshop equipped teachers with skills in differentiated instruction, technology integration, and project-based learning. Led by an Instructional Coach, this program aimed to cater to diverse learning needs and enhance instructional effectiveness across classrooms.

The Effective Classroom Management Training focused on enhancing teachers' abilities to create positive learning environments and manage classroom dynamics effectively. This program, spearheaded by the School Administrator, provided essential skills to maintain order and maximize instructional time.

Lastly, the Data-Driven Instruction Workshop trained teachers in analyzing student data to inform instructional decisions. Led by a School Administrator and Supervisor, this program aimed to enhance teaching effectiveness through evidence-based practices and targeted interventions based on student performance data.

Conclusions

In examining perceptions regarding instructional competence between Master teachers and teachers across various domains, the study revealed no statistically significant differences. Master teachers have been noted for connecting current content with past and future lessons, enhancing students' comprehension within a broader educational context. Their ability to maintain continuity in learning and emphasize curriculum progression over time has been highlighted as a significant strength. Similarly, perceptions of both Master teachers and teachers regarding teaching strategy skills had shown a cohesive approach in aligning instructional methods and resources to achieve learning objectives effectively. Concerning classroom management skills, Master teachers have been recognized for their capability to cultivate disciplined learning environments conducive to student engagement and responsibility. Their strategies in establishing clear expectations and managing classroom dynamics had been perceived similarly to those employed by teachers. Furthermore, in evaluation skills, both groups had been viewed as proficient in designing and implementing assessment practices that accurately assessed student progress and guided instructional decisions. In terms of mentoring skills, Master teachers have been acknowledged for their role in providing emotional support and professional guidance within educational settings. They have been noted for fostering collaborative learning environments and supporting colleagues' professional growth. These findings underscored a shared perception of high instructional competence between Master teachers and teachers across the examined domains. Statistical analyses, including t-values and interpretations, confirmed that these perceptions' mean differences were not statistically significant. This indicated a strong alignment in how Master teachers and teachers were perceived as technical assistance providers within educational contexts. Accepting the null hypothesis for each comparison, the study conclusively determined that there had been no substantive distinction in the perceived instructional competence between Master teachers and teachers based on the statistical findings provided. Overall, these findings highlighted the effectiveness and proficiency of both Master teachers and teachers in their instructional roles. Their shared competence as technical assistance providers underscored their contributions to student learning outcomes and professional development within the teaching community. This alignment in perceptions reaffirmed the pivotal role of Master teachers and teachers in shaping educational experiences and fostering continuous improvement in teaching practices.

Based on the conclusion drawn from the study on perceptions of instructional competence between Master teachers and teachers, several recommendations can be made to enhance educational practices further and support professional development within the teaching community. Firstly, promoting collaborative professional development is essential. Establishing regular meetings or workshops where Master teachers and teachers can share insights, best practices, and innovative teaching methods will foster a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement. This knowledge exchange can significantly enhance instructional strategies and curriculum development across schools. Secondly, fostering mentoring programs is crucial for nurturing new teachers. Formalized mentorship pairs Master teachers with less experienced colleagues to guide instructional techniques, emotional support, and career development. Structured mentoring can accelerate new educators' professional growth and retention rates, ultimately benefiting teachers and students. Continuous training in diverse instructional strategies should also be prioritized. Offering workshops and professional development opportunities on differentiated instruction, technology integration, project-based learning, and other effective

methodologies ensures that teachers remain adaptable and responsive to evolving educational needs. This empowers educators to cater to diverse learning styles and maximize student engagement and achievement. Enhancing classroom management skills is another critical recommendation. Providing specialized training in effective classroom management techniques equips teachers with strategies to create positive learning environments, manage student behavior proactively, and foster a culture of respect and productivity in the classroom. Strong classroom management skills contribute significantly to student outcomes and overall school climate. Reflective practice should be encouraged among Master teachers and teachers. Promoting a culture where educators regularly assess their teaching methods, seek feedback from peers and students, and adjust their approaches based on evidence enhances instructional effectiveness. This reflective approach supports continuous improvement and ensures that teaching practices are continually refined to meet the needs of diverse learners. Data-driven instructional decision-making is another essential recommendation. Offering training on analyzing student data, identifying learning gaps, and tailoring instructional strategies accordingly empowers educators to make informed decisions that optimize student learning outcomes. Utilizing data effectively ensures that instructional practices are evidence-based and responsive to student needs. Supporting emotional intelligence and creating supportive classroom environments is critical. Providing resources and training to build positive relationships, address social-emotional learning needs, and foster inclusive classrooms enhances student well-being and academic success. Educators prioritizing emotional intelligence create a nurturing learning environment where every student feels valued and supported. Empowering teacher leadership is vital for driving educational innovation. Recognizing Master teachers as leaders within schools or districts and providing opportunities for them to lead professional learning communities, mentor peers, and contribute to curriculum design fosters a culture of collaboration and expertise sharing. Teacher leadership enhances professional growth and promotes school-wide instructional excellence. Encouraging cross-disciplinary collaboration among Master teachers and teachers from different subject areas enriches professional growth. Facilitating opportunities for educators to collaborate on interdisciplinary projects and share diverse perspectives strengthens instructional practices and promotes holistic student learning experiences. Lastly, investing in professional growth opportunities is essential. Allocating resources for Master teachers and teachers to attend conferences, pursue advanced certifications, and engage in research or innovative projects stimulates creativity and expertise in instructional practices. This investment supports lifelong learning and ensures educators remain at the forefront of educational best practices. By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can cultivate a supportive and collaborative environment where Master teachers and teachers continuously enhance their instructional competence. This approach benefits teacher professional development and enhances student achievement and overall educational outcomes, ultimately contributing to the success of the entire learning community.

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